

ANTI-BLAST DESIGN OF CELLULAR SACRIFICIAL CLADDING BASED ON A NONLINEAR PLASTIC SHOCK MODEL

Yuanyuan Ding¹, Shilong Wang¹, Zhijun Zheng^{1,*}, Liming Yang² and Jilin Yu¹

¹CAS Key Laboratory of Mechanical Behavior and Design of Materials, University of Science and Technology of China, Hefei 230026, PR China

²Mechanics and Materials Science Research Center, Ningbo University, Ningbo 315211, PR China

* Corresponding author. Email: zjzheng@ustc.edu.cn (Z.J. Zheng)

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ABSTRACT

Cellular sacrificial cladding with rational design could effectively attenuate impact/blast loadings. Dimensional analysis was employed to guide its anti-blast design in this study and a nonlinear plastic shock model was further applied to refine the design method. It is considered that a cellular sacrificial cladding is made of a cellular core and two cover plates: one cover plate is subjected to a triangular pressure pulse and the other cover plate is fixed. Cellular material was modeled by a rate-independent, rigid-plastic hardening (R-PH) idealization with two material parameters, namely the initial crush stress and the strain hardening parameter. Dimensional analysis was carried out to study the critical length of cellular sacrificial cladding, which could attenuate a given blast loading completely. A shock model based on the R-PH idealization was developed and an equation governing the shock wave propagation in the sacrificial cladding was obtained and solved numerically with a fourth-order Runge-Kutta scheme. An empirical expression of the critical length of cellular sacrificial cladding was determined. It is compared to that predicted from the shock model based on the rate-independent, rigid-perfectly plastic-locking (R-PP-L) idealization. The energy absorption mechanism of cellular sacrificial cladding was explored by shock propagation theory. The results reveal that the attached mass and the strength of blast load are very important for the cellular sacrificial cladding design. This method of anti-blast design of the cellular sacrificial cladding was verified using cell-based finite element models based on three-dimensional Voronoi technology.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cellular sacrificial cladding, which is composed by a cellular core and two cover plates, has been widely adopted in civil and military applications to protect the structures from impact/blast damage[1,2]. There are two typical dynamic features of cellular materials, namely shock enhancement and deformation localization. Due to these features, a cellular sacrificial cladding made through suitable design may absorb massive impact/blast energy and protect the main structure from destruction when it suffers impact/blast loading. The main consideration in the design of cellular sacrificial cladding is to assure that the stress reaching the protected structure is controlled within an allowable range.

A debate on whether cellular materials could be used as a protecting cladding to attenuate the

blast load can be found in the literature. Several experimental phenomena have highlighted the fact that the cellular material could result in stress enhancement instead of load alleviation [3-5]. However, Harrigan et al. [6] did not agree with this point, and they pointed out that the stress enhancement would not take place at the distal end of cellular sacrificial cladding unless the cellular core had been compressed tightly. Therefore, a rational design for cellular sacrificial cladding is important and necessary for avoiding the stress enhancement at the distal end. In 2002, Hanssen et al. [7] obtained the critical length of cladding based on the rate-independent, rigid-perfectly plastic-locking (R-PP-L) shock model. Ma and Ye [8] proposed a double-layer foam cladding which composed of two layers with different foam densities and two additional plates. Furthermore, Liao et al. [9] presented a design guide of double-layer cellular cladding for blast alleviation based on the R-PP-L shock model, and the comparison with the cell-based finite element model of Voronoi honeycombs shows that the R-PP-L shock model overestimates the energy absorption capability of cellular materials.

The R-PP-L shock model was first proposed by Reid and Peng [10] to describe the dynamic response of wood. For its practicality and simplicity, this model has been applied to analyze other cellular materials and was validated by a series of experiments [11]. Although the R-PP-L shock model could explain several dynamic mechanisms of cellular materials, it could only present a first-order approximation for engineering design. Besides the R-PP-L shock model, a series of much accurate shock models [12-16] have been proposed to characterize the dynamic responses of cellular materials. For example, Zheng et al. [16] recently proposed a rate-independent, rigid-plastic hardening (R-PH) idealization and a rate-dependent one (a D-R-PH idealization) to describe the quasi-static and dynamic stress-strain curves of cellular materials and obtained the corresponding shock models.

In this paper, the R-PH idealization is used to estimate the energy absorption capability of cellular sacrificial cladding, and the anti-blast design guide of cellular sacrificial cladding is proposed for the engineering protection.

2 PLASTIC SHOCK MODEL

2.1 Stress-strain relations of cellular materials

Cellular materials have superior capacity of energy absorption due to its long plastic stress plateau. Since the dynamic stress-strain relation of cellular materials is not much clear, the quasi-static one is commonly used in applications to guide the design of energy absorption structures. The R-PP-L idealization [10] is the most popular one. It only has two material parameters, namely the initial crushing stress (or the plateau stress) σ_0 and the locking strain (or the densification strain) ε_D , but it could characterize the compressive behavior of cellular materials in a first-order approximation. However, the response predicted by this model is sensitive to the choice of locking strain.

To improve the practicability of energy absorption structures, the nonlinear plastic hardening and the rate effects of cellular materials [16] should be considered. In this study, we only focus on the effect of the nonlinear plastic hardening of cellular materials. A more accurate material model, i.e. the R-PH idealization [16], is employed to characterize the nominal stress-strain curve of cellular materials, written as

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 + \frac{C\varepsilon}{(1-\varepsilon)^2}, \quad (1)$$

where σ_0 is the initial crushing stress and C is the strain hardening parameter.

2.2 Anti-blast model of cellular sacrificial cladding

The explosion loading could be approximated as a plane pressure wave when the loading takes place at a certain distance away from the cladding. In general, the blast load pressure is simplified as a triangle pulse wave [7,8]:

$$p(t) = \begin{cases} p_0(1-t/t_0), & 0 \leq t \leq t_0 \\ 0, & t > t_0 \end{cases}, \quad (2)$$

where t is the time, p_0 the initial peak of blast load and t_0 the duration of blast load.

A cellular sacrificial cladding is made of a cellular core and two cover plates: one cover plate is subjected to the pressure pulse and the other cover plate is fixed on the protected structure. For convenience of analysis, the cover plate close to the protected structure is considered as the fixed end of the cladding, as shown in Fig. 1. The cellular core deforms as a 1D shock front propagating from the loading end to the fixed end when a blast load acts on the cellular sacrificial cladding. The blast load becomes weakened and then vanishes at $t = t_0$. Due to the residual kinetic energy in the part behind the shock front, the shock front continues to propagate until the kinetic energy of the system completely vanishes. By using the law of the conservation of momentum, the total blast load acting on the cladding is related to the impulse absorbed by the cellular sacrificial cladding: $p_0 t_0 / 2 = \sigma_0 t_m$, where t_m is the end time, at which the blast load is completely absorbed by the cellular sacrificial cladding. From this relation, the end time is determined as $t_m = p_0 t_0 / (2\sigma_0)$.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of cellular sacrificial cladding for blast alleviation [17].

Assuming the cover plate is a rigid body and the X coordinate is established at the interface of the cover plate and the cellular core, as shown in Fig. 1. At time t , the shock front arrives at $u + x$, and thus the velocity of shock front is

$$C_s = \frac{d(u+x)}{dt} = \frac{dl}{dt}, \quad (3)$$

where u is the displacement of cover plate, x is the thickness of the compaction region in the cellular material, and l is the undeformed length of the cellular material.

The sectional area A of the cellular material is assumed to be unchanged throughout the

deformation process. According to the mass conservation law, the relationship of the density ρ behind the shock wave and the density ρ_0 ahead of the shock wave can be expressed as

$$\rho = \rho_0 / (1 - \varepsilon), \quad (4)$$

where ε is the strain behind the shock wave.

By considering a small time interval from t to $t + dt$, the corresponding mass m_1 of the small element swept by the shock front is

$$dm_1 = \rho dx = -\rho_0 dl. \quad (5)$$

Dividing dt on both sides of the above equation, and combining with Eq. (3), we have

$$\frac{dl}{dt} = -\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \left(\frac{dl}{dt} + \frac{du}{dt} \right), \quad (6)$$

which could be further expressed as

$$\frac{dl}{dt} = \frac{\rho}{\rho_0 - \rho} \frac{du}{dt} = -\frac{1}{\varepsilon} \frac{du}{dt} = -\frac{v}{\varepsilon} = -C_s, \quad (7)$$

where $v = du/dt$ is the particle velocity behind the shock front. During the time interval dt , the impulse exerted by the forces on both sides of the small element is equal to the change of the element's momentum

$$dm_1 \cdot A(v + dv) - 0 = (\sigma_D - \sigma_0) A dt, \quad (8)$$

where σ_D is the densification stress. Dividing the area A on the both sides, neglecting the second order term $dm_1 dv$ and combining with Eqs. (5) and (7), we have

$$\sigma_D = \sigma_0 + \rho_0 \frac{v^2}{\varepsilon}. \quad (9)$$

Similarly, the momentum conservation of the rigid body (the cover plate and the compressive region in the cellular material) at time t gives

$$\left[m + \rho_0(u+x) \right] \frac{dv}{dt} + (\sigma_D - p(t)) = 0, \quad (10)$$

where m is the mass per unit area of the cover plate.

Combining Eqs. (1), (7), (9) and (10) leads to a differential equation

$$\left[m + \rho_0(c_1 t + u) \right] \frac{d^2 u}{dt^2} + \rho_0 \left(c_1 + \frac{du}{dt} \right) \frac{du}{dt} + \sigma_0 - p(t) = 0, \quad (11)$$

where $c_1 = (C/\rho_0)^{1/2}$. This equation is the governing equation of the anti-blast of the cellular sacrificial cladding based on the R-PH idealization, and the initial conditions are $u(0) = 0$ and $v(0) = 0$. However, there is no explicit solution to this differential equation, and it would be solved numerically with a fourth-order Runge-Kutta scheme.

3 CELL-BASED FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

Closed-cell foam with a uniform cell-wall thickness is generated by using the 3D Voronoi technique, see Ref. [16] for details. Numerical simulations were performed by using the finite element

code ABAQUS/Explicit. The cell-wall material is assumed to be elastic, perfectly plastic with $E = 69$ GPa, $Y = 170$ MPa, $\rho_s = 2700$ kg/m³ and $\nu = 0.3$, where E , Y and ν are the Young's modulus, yield stress and Poisson's ratio, respectively. The cell walls of Voronoi structures are meshed by using shell elements (Types S3R and S4R). The relative density of the Voronoi structure used in numerical simulations is set as $\rho_0/\rho_s = 0.1$, where ρ_0 is the initial density of the Voronoi structures and ρ_s the density of the cell-wall material.

The macroscopic properties could be simulated by using a Voronoi structure with at least five cells along the shortest length direction. So, the cellular specimen used in this study is constructed in a volume of $30 \times 20 \times 20$ mm³ with 600 nuclei. The quasi-static nominal stress-strain curve could be obtained by the numerical compression test ($V = 1$ m/s, i.e. the corresponding strain rate is about 33 /s). Therefore, the parameters of the R-PH idealization could be determined by the curve-fitting method ($\sigma_0 = 5.99$ MPa and $C = 0.499$ MPa), and the parameters of R-PP-L idealization are the initial crushing stress $\sigma_0 = 5.99$ MPa and the densification strain $\varepsilon_D = 0.640$, where the densification strain is determined as the strain associated with maximum energy absorption efficiency. From Fig. 2, it is clear that the R-PH idealization is better than the R-PP-L idealization to describe the quasi-static nominal stress-strain curve of the cellular material.

Figure 2: The quasi-static nominal stress–strain curve obtained from the cell-based finite element model and the R-PP-L and R-PH idealizations.

A finite element model of cellular sacrificial cladding for blast alleviation is showed in Fig. 3. The cellular sacrificial cladding is fixed at the left end on a rigid wall and is covered by a right mass at the right end. The blast loading acts on the outer surface of the rigid mass.

Figure 3: A finite element model of cellular sacrificial cladding for blast alleviation.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Dimensional analysis of cellular sacrificial cladding

An important parameter, namely the critical length of cellular sacrificial cladding, plays a key role in the engineering design. Based on the R-PP-L shock model, the critical thickness of the single cellular sacrificial cladding was obtained as [7, 9]

$$L_0 = \frac{m}{\rho_0} \left[\sqrt{1 + \frac{S}{\varepsilon_D} \left(1 - \frac{4\sigma_0}{3p_0} \right)} - 1 \right], \quad p_0 > 2\sigma_0, \quad (12)$$

where S is a dimensionless parameter, namely shock-enhancement factor [9], defined as

$$S = \frac{\rho_0 (p_0 t_0 / 2m)^2}{\sigma_0}, \quad (13)$$

in which $p_0 t_0 / (2m)$ is the maximum velocity that the cover plate may reach when the total impulse is transferred to the cover plate without the cellular material. The shock-enhancement factor S represents the ratio of the shock enhancement of the cellular material with its maximum velocity and the initial crushing stress of the cellular material. It directly reflects the loading intensity with respect to the initial crushing stress of the cellular material.

As there is no explicit solution of cellular sacrificial cladding based on the R-PH shock model, dimensional analysis method is introduced to analyze the critical length of cellular sacrificial cladding L_{cr} in this section. The critical length L_{cr} should be related to the mass of the cover plate m , the blast load parameters (the initial peak p_0 and the duration t_0), and the mechanical parameters of the cellular material (the density ρ_0 , the initial crushing stress σ_0 and the strain hardening parameter C), written as

$$L_{cr} = f(\rho_0, \sigma_0, C; p_0, t_0; m). \quad (14)$$

The dimensions of these parameters are listed in Table 1, in which L, M and T are the dimensions of length, mass and time, respectively.

Parameters	L_{cr}	ρ_0	σ_0	C	p_0	t_0	m
Dimension	L	ML^{-3}	$ML^{-1}T^{-2}$	$ML^{-1}T^{-2}$	$ML^{-1}T^{-2}$	T	ML^{-2}

Table 1: The dimensions of the parameters for cellular sacrificial cladding.

From the light of Eq. (12) predicted from R-PP-L shock model, we learn that the dimensionless critical length $L_0/(m/\rho_0)$ is a function of three dimensionless parameters (σ_0/p_0 , ε_D , S). As the shock-enhancement factor S is a large number, while $\varepsilon_D \sim 1$ and $0 < \sigma_0/p_0 < 1/2$, we further learn that the leading order of $L_0/(m/\rho_0)$ is $S^{1/2}$. Thus, for the R-PH shock model, we take C/σ_0 instead of ε_D and reach the following dimensionless relationship

$$\frac{L_{cr}}{m/\rho_0} = f\left(\frac{\sigma_0}{p_0}, \frac{C}{\sigma_0}, \sqrt{S}\right). \quad (15)$$

In the following analysis, we denote the three dimensionless parameters as

$$\alpha = \sigma_0 / p_0, \quad \beta = C / \sigma_0, \quad \gamma = \sqrt{S}. \quad (16)$$

Considering the physical meanings and the possible values of the parameters in the anti-blast system of cellular sacrificial cladding may help to obtain an empirical form of the function in Eq. (15). First, the end time of the anti-blast process $t_m = p_0 t_0 / (2\sigma_0) > t_0$, which means the initial peak of loading p_0 is at least twice as large as σ_0 . Second, the strain hardening parameter C is an order of magnitude smaller than σ_0 . Third, the shock-enhancement factor S directly reflects the loading intensity with respect to the initial crushing stress of the cellular material. In general, the blast impulse is very intense and thus shock-enhancement factor S is very large. Therefore, we set $S > 8$ and ignore the case when the blast load is very small, namely $S < 8$. In this study, the variations of dimensionless parameters are chosen as $0.075 < \alpha < 0.3$, $0.04 < \beta < 0.2$ and $3.7 < \gamma < 20$.

In order to obtain the relationship between the dimensionless critical length and the three dimensionless parameters in Eq. (15), controlling variable method is adopted. First, the influence of γ on the dimensionless critical length is analyzed and the results determined from the R-PH shock model are given in Fig. 4a, in which we take $\alpha = 20/3$ and $\beta = 1/30 \sim 2/15$. It shows that the dimensionless critical length $L_{cr}/(m/\rho_0)$ increases linearly with the increase of γ for the given values of α and β . Thus, we assume that the dimensionless critical length could be expressed by

$$\frac{L_{cr}}{m/\rho_0} = w_1(\alpha, \beta)\gamma + w_2(\alpha, \beta), \quad (17)$$

where w_1 and w_2 are unknown functions of α and β .

Similarly, the influence of α on the dimensionless critical length is analyzed by fixing the values of β and γ . It could be found that there is another linear relationship between the critical length parameter and the dimensionless parameter α , as shown in Fig. 4b. Thus, Eq. (17) could be further written as

$$\frac{L_{cr}}{m/\rho_0} = (g_1(\beta)\alpha + g_2(\beta))\gamma + g_3(\beta)\alpha + g_4(\beta), \quad (18)$$

where $g_1(\beta)$, $g_2(\beta)$, $g_3(\beta)$ and $g_4(\beta)$ are undetermined functions with respect of β .

Figure 4: Variations of the dimensionless critical length $L_{cr}/(m/\rho_0)$ with the dimensionless parameter γ (a) and the dimensionless parameter α (b).

The empirical functions $g_1(\beta)$, $g_2(\beta)$, $g_3(\beta)$, $g_4(\beta)$ are obtained by the least squares method with $0.083 < \alpha < 0.25$ and $3.7 < \gamma < 20$, shown in Fig. 5, which exhibit that the magnitudes of $g_1(\beta)$, $g_2(\beta)$, $g_3(\beta)$ and $g_4(\beta)$ are $O(1)$ and their variations are very small with the increase of β . The functions of $g_1(\beta)$, $g_2(\beta)$, $g_3(\beta)$, $g_4(\beta)$ are linearly fitted as

$$\begin{cases} g_1(\beta) = -0.958 - 0.522\beta \\ g_2(\beta) = 1.14 + 1.22\beta \\ g_3(\beta) = 1.23 + 1.28\beta \\ g_4(\beta) = -0.929 + 0.0668\beta \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

To further simplify the expression of Eq. (18), the magnitude relations of the four terms in Eq.(18) are analyzed and expressed as

$$\frac{-g_1(\beta)\alpha\gamma}{g_2(\beta)\gamma} \sim \frac{g_3(\beta)\alpha}{-g_4(\beta)} \sim \alpha \sim 0.1, \quad \frac{g_1(\beta)\alpha\gamma}{g_4(\beta)} \sim O(1). \quad (20)$$

Obviously, $g_2(\beta)\gamma$ is the leading term for the dimensionless critical length $L_{cr}/(m/\rho_0)$ in Eq. (18), $g_1(\beta)\alpha\gamma$ and $g_4(\beta)$ are secondary contributions, and $g_3(\beta)\alpha$ is an negligible term. Noticing $\beta \sim 0.1$, the linear terms of $g_1(\beta)$ and $g_4(\beta)$ could also be negligible compared with their constant terms in Eq. (19). Thus, we could further assume the final expression of Eq. (18) as

$$\frac{L_{cr}}{m/\rho_0} = (a + b\alpha + c\beta)\gamma + d, \quad (21)$$

where a , b , c , d are new pending coefficients, which could be recalculated by the least squares method with the above mentioned variations of α , β and γ . Thus, the empirical expression of the critical length of cellular sacrificial cladding is determined and expressed as

$$\frac{L_{cr}}{m/\rho_0} = \left(1.13 + 1.18 \frac{C}{\sigma_0} - 0.864 \frac{\sigma_0}{\rho_0} \right) \sqrt{S} - 0.821. \quad (22)$$

In comparison with the exact result predicted by the R-PH shock model, the maximum relative error of the fitting result presented in Eq. (22) is no more than 5%.

Figure 5: Variations of $g_1(\beta)$, $g_2(\beta)$, $g_3(\beta)$ and $g_4(\beta)$ with the dimensionless parameter β .

4.2 Energy absorption mechanism

According to the energy conservation relation across a shock front based on the shock wave theory, the internal energy per unit volume can be expressed as [18]

$$\Delta U = \frac{1}{2}(\sigma^- + \sigma^+)(\varepsilon^- - \varepsilon^+), \quad (23)$$

where superscripts “+” and “-” denote the value ahead of and behind the shock wave, respectively. For the R-PP-L shock model, the internal energy per unit volume is obtained as

$$\Delta U = \sigma_0 \varepsilon_D + \frac{1}{2} \rho_0 v^2, \quad (24)$$

where v is the particle velocity of the cellular material behind the shock front in this study. For the R-PH shock model, the internal energy per unit volume could be expressed as

$$\Delta U = \frac{\sigma_0 v}{c_1 + v} + \frac{1}{2} \rho_0 v^2. \quad (25)$$

There is a critical velocity $v_c = \varepsilon_D c_1 / (1 - \varepsilon_D) = 76.4$ m/s by combining Eq. (24) with Eq. (25), at which the energy absorptions predicted by the R-PP-L and R-PH shock models are the same.

Figure 6: Time history of energy absorption of cellular sacrificial cladding with different attached masses (a) and under different blast loads (b), respectively.

For the cellular sacrificial cladding system, the influences of external parameters (the cover plate mass and the blast load parameters) to the energy absorbed by the cellular material are discussed here. First, the energy absorption of cellular sacrificial cladding with different cover plate masses, which are 5.4, 16.2, and 27 kg/m² respectively, are plotted in Fig. 6a. The results show that more energy is needed to be absorbed by the cladding when the plate mass is smaller. This is because that the attached mass influences the total work done by the blast load. According to the momentum conservation law, the total work done by the load or the final energy absorbed by the cladding has a negative correlation with the cover plate mass. Second, considering a series of blast loads (the initial peaks are 80, 40 and 20 MPa, with the blast times of 0.3, 0.6 and 1.2 ms, respectively, to make sure the explosion impulses $p_0 t_0 / 2$ are the same), the time history of energy absorption is shown in Fig. 6b. The results indicate that the energy absorption of cladding has a positive correlation with the strength of blast load. According

to Eq. (25), the velocity discontinuous jump across the shock wave plays a key role on the energy absorption of cellular sacrificial cladding. Improving the initial strength of the blast load may increase the velocity of the compacted part of cellular material, and a short blast time may result in a slightly decrease of the velocity. Therefore, reducing the attached mass or increasing the peak of blast load (explosion impulse remains unchanged) will result in an increase of the energy to be absorbed by the cellular sacrificial cladding.

4.3 Comparison with finite element results

The validation of the cellular sacrificial cladding theoretical results based on the R-PH shock model is verified by the cell-based numerical simulation. The simulation parameters are set as: the initial peak of blast load $p_0 = 20$ MPa, the duration $t_0 = 0.3$ ms and the cover plate mass $m = 5.4$ kg/m². A 3D Voronoi structure is taken as the core material of cladding, as shown in Fig. 3. According to Eqs. (11) and (12), the critical lengths of cellular sacrificial cladding based on the R-PP-L and R-PH shock models are 55.0 mm and 57.6 mm, respectively. The section of the finite element model is 10×10 mm², so the attached mass is 0.54 g.

A comparison between the cell-based finite element results and the analytical predictions is shown in Fig. 7. From Fig. 7a, the analytical predictions obtained from the R-PH shock model underestimate the velocity of the attached mass. The time history of the stress at the fixed end obtained from the finite element results is consistent with the analytical predictions when $t < 0.35$ ms, but a stress enhancement at the end of the deformation process is observed, as shown in Fig. 7b. The results reveal that the cellular sacrificial cladding based on the R-PH model is not thick enough for the specific blast load, and the design based on the R-PP-L model is even worse for its earlier and stronger stress enhancement. Therefore, considering the strain hardening effect would improve the accuracy of cellular sacrificial cladding design, but it is insufficient. The dynamic constitutive effects [16] should be taken into consideration to improve the accuracy of the theoretical shock model in further study. In addition, there are some inadequacies when the shock model is considered in the whole analysis process. From Fig. 7a, at the beginning and the end of anti-blast processes, the velocities of the attached mass are low, at which the deformation mode of cellular materials is in a homogeneous or transition mode [13, 15]. The corresponding deformation patterns are shown in Fig. 8, and the random shear collapse bands appear obviously in the cellular material at $t = 0.352$ ms.

Figure 7: Comparison between the cell-based finite element (FE) results and the analytical predictions obtained from the R-PH shock model: the velocity of the attached mass (a) and the support stress (b).

Figure 8: Deformation patterns of cellular sacrificial cladding ($L_{cr} = 57.6$ mm) obtained from the cell-based finite element model.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The anti-blast ability of cellular sacrificial cladding is investigated and analyzed based on the rate-independent R-PH shock model. A differential equation governing the shock front propagation in the cellular sacrificial cladding is obtained, which reveals the shock front propagation characteristics in the cladding. An empirical expression of the critical length of cellular sacrificial cladding is determined by dimensional analysis method using the data obtained from the R-PH shock model, and the result shows that the square root of shock-enhancement factor is the main dominant term for $L_{cr}/(m/\rho_0)$. The energy absorption mechanism of cellular sacrificial cladding is explored, which shows that the velocity discontinuous jump across the shock wave plays a key role on the energy absorption based on the R-PH shock model. The influences of the attached mass and the strength of blast load to energy absorption of cladding are analyzed, and the results reveal that increasing the additional mass may be beneficial for anti-blast design of cellular sacrificial cladding. The numerical results based on the cell-based finite element model of closed-cell foams are generally consistent with the theoretical predictions for anti-blast process of cellular sacrificial cladding, which shows the effectiveness and correctness of anti-blast design of cladding by using the R-PH shock model.

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